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A STUDY ON WOMEN ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT THROUGH SELF HELP GROUP

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Just a bird could not fly with its one wing only; a nation would not march forward if women were left behind

- Swami Vivekanand

Abstract

This conceptual paper indicates and emphasizes the women entrepreneurs as the potentially emerging human resource in the 21st century. The primary objective of this paper is to find out the status of women entrepreneurs in India and the challenges faced by them. This paper includes rationale grounds behind the women entrepreneurship and also to study the characteristics of Women Entrepreneurs in India. Another main purpose of this study focused on the Role of Self Help Groups in Women Entrepreneurship Development and also to understand meaning, origin and features of SHG. On the basis of this study some suggestions and conclusions are given to encourage spirit of women entrepreneurship and helping them to become a successful entrepreneur.

Keywords: *Women entrepreneurship, Challenges, Reasons, Characteristics, Role of SHGs,*

Introduction

Rural women in India constitute 77 percent of the female population. For long time women had been deprived of any status in the society. Women's traditional skills tended become obsolete and they were not given equal opportunities with men to acquire modern skills and equipment. The Committee appointed by the government of India to assess the status of women might in India pointed out that over the first 10 years of 20th century, the insignificant economic dependency, illiteracy, lack of skill, and lack of access to training. In this context one of the best ways to women empowerment is the functioning of Self Help Groups. Self help is not a new concept in India. Starting from Mahatma Gandhi, Jayaprakash Narayan many leaders have preached and practiced Self Help.

Objectives and Research Methodology of the Study

The study is based on secondary data which is collected from the published reports of RBI, NABARD, Census Surveys, SSI Reports, newspapers, journals, websites, etc.

The study was planned with the following objectives:

1. To explore the Status of women entrepreneurs in India.
2. To find the Challenges faced by women entrepreneurs.
3. To find out the Reasons for Women to Become Entrepreneurs.
4. To study the characteristics of Women Entrepreneurs in India.
5. To study the Role of Self Help Groups in Women Entrepreneurial Development
6. To draw suggestions and conclusions.

Women Entrepreneurship

Women entrepreneurship is the process where women organize a business or industry and provide employment opportunities to others. Women entrepreneurs can engaged in both unorganized and organized sectors. The Definition given by Govt. of India about women entrepreneurship, "An enterprise owned and controlled by a Women and having a minimum financial interest of 51% of the capital & giving at least 51 % of the employment generated in the enterprise to Women". In India only 8 percent of the small scale-manufacturing units are run

exclusively by women entrepreneurs which is proportionately very small as compared to others developed and developing countries. In USA about 50 percent of the business is owned by women.

Status of Women Entrepreneurs in India

Entrepreneurship is considered as one of the most important factors contributing to the development of society. India has been ranked among the worst performing countries in the area of women entrepreneurship in gender-focused global entrepreneurship survey, released in July 2013 by PC maker Dell and Washington based consulting firm Global Entrepreneurship and Development Institute (GEDI). Of the 17 countries surveyed India ranks 16th, just above Uganda. Countries like Turkey, Morocco and Egypt have outperformed India. Status of higher education in women in India came out to be lower than most countries in the world. At present, women's entrepreneurial role is limited in the large scale industries and technology based businesses. But even in small scale industries, the women's participation is very low. As per the third all-India census of Small Scale Industries, only 10.11% of the micro and small enterprises were owned by women, and only 9.46% of them were managed by women. While the number of women operating their own business is increasing globally, women continue to face huge obstacles that stunt the growth of their businesses, such as lack of capital, strict social constraints, and limited time and skill.

Challenges Faced by Women Entrepreneurs

Entrepreneurship is a herculean task which is fraught with struggle, entailing both risk and effort. No one can truly understand the triumphs, trials and tribulation of entrepreneur other than the person involved. While women have to go through the same stages of setting up an enterprise and do men, and have similar challenges, irrespective of gender, women do have a distinct set of factors that first impede their entry as entrepreneurs, and later their survival as successful business women. In women entrepreneurial abilities are not always approved by their family, workloads are exhausting with the double burden of taking care of home and family, as well as earning livelihood, women have lack of access to resources, raw materials, new technology and markets, then women are enter into competition with less knowledge and training than their male counterparts.

Reasons for Women to become Entrepreneurs

Self esteem, recognition, Self determination, and career goal are the key drivers for choosing to entrepreneurship by women. Sometimes, women choose such career path for proving their potential, caliber in order to achieve self satisfaction. However, dismal economic conditions of the women arising out of unemployment in the family and divorce can compel women into entrepreneurial activities. The days have gone when women always passed her whole life within the boundaries of house now women are found indulged in every line of business. The entry of women into business in India is an extension of their normal home activities. But with the spread of education and passage of time women started shifting from doing work at home or kitchen to the business venture. Skill, knowledge and adaptability in business are the main reasons for women to emerge into business ventures. Women Entrepreneur is a person who accepts challenging role to meet her personal needs and become economically independent. A strong desire to do something positive is an inbuilt quality of entrepreneurial women, who is capable of contributing values in both family and social life. With the advent of media, women are aware of their own traits, rights and also the work situations. The challenges and opportunities provided to the women of digital era are growing rapidly that the job seekers are turning into job creators. Many women start a business due to some traumatic event, such as divorce, discrimination due to pregnancy or the corporate glass ceiling, the health of a family member, or economic reasons such as a layoff. But a new talent pool of women entrepreneurs is forming today, as more women opt to leave corporate world to chart their own destinies. They are growing as designers, interior decorators, exporters, publishers, garment manufacturers and still exploring new avenues of economic participation.

Characteristics of Women Entrepreneurs in India

The following important characteristics of women entrepreneurs in India are:

1. Management and Control: A woman or a group of women manages the whole business of enterprise. She prepares various plans and executes them under her own supervision and control. There may be some persons to help her but ultimate control lies with the woman.

2. Employment to Women: A woman entrepreneur must provide at least 51 percent of the employment generated in her enterprise to women.

3. Risk-taking: Risk means uncertainty. It is the condition of not knowing the outcome of an activity. A woman entrepreneur takes calculated risk. She faces uncertainty confidently and assumes risk. She has to tie up capital and wait for good returns. A woman entrepreneur likes to take realistic risks because she wants to be a successful entrepreneur.

4. Good organizer: The most critical skill required for industrial development is the ability of building a sound organization. A woman entrepreneur assembles, co-ordinates, organizes and manages the other factors namely land, labor and capital. She obtains factors of production from the society and supplies them finished product.

5. Self confidence: It is essential to be a self confident for a woman entrepreneur. She should have faith in herself and in her abilities. She should have the confidence to implement the change and overcome any resistance to change. A woman entrepreneur should have courage to own the mistakes and correct them.

6. Decision-maker: The main function of a woman entrepreneur is to make decision. She takes various decisions regarding the activities of her enterprise. She decides about the type of business to be done and the way of doing it. A woman entrepreneur must be clear and creative in decision making process.

7. Visionary: A woman entrepreneur is one who incubates new ideas, starts her enterprise with these ideas and provides added value to society based on their independent initiative.

8. Hard worker: A distinguishing feature of a woman entrepreneur is the willingness to work hard. She has to follow the principle, "Hard-work is the key to success".

9. Achievement oriented: A woman entrepreneur is an achievement oriented lady, not money hungry. She works for challenge, accomplishment and service to others. Achievement orientation is a derive to overcome challenges, to advance and to grow.

10. Optimistic: A woman entrepreneur must be optimistic. She should approach her venture with a hope of success and attitude for success rather than with a fear of failure. The positive thinking of woman entrepreneur can turn the situation favorable to her.

11. Technically competent: The success of an enterprise largely depends upon the ability of woman entrepreneur to cope with latest technology. Technical competency refers to the ability to devise and use the better ways of producing and marketing goods and services.

12. Bold and brave: Women entrepreneurs face the adversities boldly and bravery. She has faith in herself and attempts to solve the problems even under great pressure.

13. Mentally sound: A woman entrepreneur is energetic, single-minded, having a mission and a clear vision. She should be a lady of creative thinking and analytical thinking. She must be intelligent, adaptable and problem solver.

14. Leadership: Leadership quality is one of the most important characteristic of a woman entrepreneur. It is the process of influencing and supporting others to work enthusiastically towards achieving objectives.

Entrepreneurship Development of Women through SHG

Strength and weakness, both are the different sides of the same coin. Hence, all involved group members of SHG must realize that they all work with their own individual strengths and weaknesses. No one should be blamed for ones weakness i.e. all SHG members are equally responsible for success and failure of their entrepreneur. Self-help group can take a lead in any of the income generating activities by which group members can get employment and enhance their family socio-economic status. The group provides a platform to women for income generation with co-operative and mutual helping attitude.

Self- Help Group

The definition of SHG as approved by National Bank For Agriculture and Rural Development [NABARD] the apex banking body in India, is “An SHG is a small, economically homogeneous and affinity group of rural poor voluntarily formed to save and mutually agree to contribute common fund to be lent to its members as per group decision for their socio-economic development”. As the name indicates, self-help group is an informal group of about 15-20 people from a homogeneous class, who come together for addressing their common problems. Group itself becomes a base to convey necessities and sort out social economical problems of their group members. Main aim of SHG is to make group members self sufficient and self reliant [independent] by self-employment and empowerment through group dynamics.

Origin of SHGs

The Origin of Self-Help Group can be traced is from Grameen bank of Bangladesh, which was founded by Mohamed Yunus. SHGs were started and formed in 1975 (Gunasekaran, 2010). In India, NABRAD initiated in 1986-87. In Tamilnadu, Chinnapillai an illiterate women live in Parparanpatti, Madurai District, initiated the feed bank of SHGs in the stats, she was honored by the former Prime Ministers of India, honorable Atal Bihari Vajpayee, for forming a group and nurtured saving habits, among the illiterate women in the village.

Features of SHG

A well functioning SHG should have following structural features:-

1. The number of members should between 10-20
2. Members should be between 21 to 60 years of age.
3. Member should live in the same village
4. Only one member per family to be covered in the SHG.
5. All the members should belong to the same socio-economic strata of society.
6. Rotational leadership should be encouraged for the distribution of power and to provide leadership opportunities to all the members.
7. Member should regularly attend meetings, save money and participate in all activities voluntarily.
8. The procedure of decision-making in SHG should democratic in nature.
9. The group frames rules and regulations, which are required in its effective functioning.
10. Transparency in account keeping and accounts should be maintained and updated regularly.
11. An SHG should be socially viable institution.
12. Members should have self interest, adjustable nature and a sense of unity

Role of SHGs in Women Entrepreneurship Development

The self-help groups empower women and train them to take active part in the socio-economic progress of the nation and make them sensitized, self-made and self disciplined. The SHGs have inculcated great confidence in the minds of rural women to succeed in their day-to-day life. SHGs enhance the quality of status of women as participants, decision makers and beneficiaries in the democratic, economic, social and cultural spheres of life. The SHGs bring out the capacity of women in molding the community in right perspective and explore the initiative of women in taking the entrepreneurial ventures. SHGs also organize women to cope with immediate purposes depending on the situation and need. Participation of women in SHGs makes a significant impact on the empowerment in social aspect also. Participation helps women come out in open and discuss their problems. It also helps to bring about awareness among rural women about savings, education, health, environment, cleanliness, family welfare, social forestry, etc. Researches also reveal that increased participation of women in decision making at all level will help to adjust the goals pursued through development. Empowerment should be extremely induced so that women can exercise a level of autonomy. There should also be ‘self empowerment’ so that women can look at their own lives. The process of ‘learning by doing and earning’ would certainly empower rural women. More and more rural women need to be involved in self-employment. Self-employment in agriculture, village and small industries and retail trade and services should be

expanded. Self-employment is also conducive to the development of individual initiative and entrepreneurial talent and offers greater personal freedom. The added advantage is that the institution of family remains undisturbed. The emergence of self-help groups in this context is a welcome development. The groups would provide a permanent forum for articulating their needs and contributing their perspectives to development.

Self-help group should be developed as an institution for financial intermediation as well as people's network rather than a vehicle for credit disbursal only. Self Help Group is able to overcome most of the practical problems encountered in the implementation of the various income generating programmes for the economic empowerment of women. SHGs have also been organized during last decade under various programmes of the government, e.g.- District Poverty Eradication Programme, Aapni yojna, Development of Women and Children in Rural Areas, Krishi Vigyan Kendra, etc. The number of SHGs existing at present in the country is estimated to be about 2,60,000. Out of these; about 90 percent are women group. The cumulative number of SHGs linked to the bank till March 2002 is 4,61,478 and to the tune of 10,263 million rupees has been advanced to the SHG for income generating activities [NABARD,2002]. As per the report of NABARD, SHG bank linkage programme has benefited 4 million families, covering an estimated 20 million very poor people during 2001-2002. The SHGs are a viable alternative to achieve the objectives of rural development and to get community participation in all rural development programmes. The possible outcomes of women's entrepreneur through SHGs at household level are self employment, sustainable livelihoods, enhanced social dignity and better status of women. SHG would lead to benefits not only to the individual women and women's groups but also for the family and community as a whole through collective action for development. Empowerment is not just for meeting their economic needs but also for more holistic social development.

Suggestions

It has been found in the study that there is only one factor i.e. skill training programmes provided by the SHGs to women has put more significant impact upon the Women Entrepreneurship Development. NGO's has to made attention towards the other factors to promote entrepreneurship. Government should help the women by providing them the ways to promote their small scale businesses. Here are some suggestive measures, to solve the problems confronted by them and for running their enterprise smoothly.

- Proper technical education to the women and opening of women development cells.
- Improvement of identification mechanism of new enterprise.
- Assistance in project formulation and follow up of training programmes.
- Credit facilities, financial incentive and subsidies.
- Adequate follow-up and support to the women enterprises.
- Women Enterprises research and application from time to time have to be documented.

Conclusions

According to the study it has been observed that Women are very good entrepreneurs, and prefer to choose the same as they can maintain work life balance. Self Help Group is an important tool which helps the rural women to acquire power for their self supportive life and nation building efforts. The empowerment of women through SHGs would lead benefits not only to the individual women but also for the family and community as whole through collection action for development these SHGs have collection action. Empowering women is not just for meeting their economic needs but also more holistic social development. The SHGs empower women and train them to take active part in socio-economic progress of the nation. Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru said, "To awaken the people, it is women who must be awakened; once she is on the move, the family moves, the village moves and nation moves." Now the women are awakened by the self help groups.

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